

THE EFFECT OF STORAGE AND TRANSPORTATION CONDITIONS OF DRIED BLOODSTAIN SAMPLES TAKEN FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF FABRY'S DISEASE ON THE RELIABILITY OF SCREENING RESULTS

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Introduction. In modern laboratory diagnostics, various technologies are used to analyze blood samples. Among them, the use of dried bloodstain (DBS) samples has advantages: they are easy to assemble, easy to transport and store for a long time. However, the reliability of the DBS sample analysis results is directly related to how they were stored and under what conditions they were transported [1,2,3]. This paper will consider the conditions for maintaining the stability of DBS samples and their impact on the results of screening tests. DBS samples are bloodstains dripping and dried on special filter paper, which are mainly used in infant screening, infectious disease diagnosis, and pharmacokinetic studies. This method increases safety when working with biomaterials and simplifies logistics. However, storage and transportation of DBS samples directly affect the reliability of the analysis results [4,5].

Materials and methods. The optimal recommended temperature for long-term storage of DBS samples is -20°C to $+25^{\circ}\text{C}$. They should be stored in the dark and dry. These conditions slow down the degradation of biological components such as enzymes, proteins, or DNA/RNA. the arsenal and research methods. Conversely, in DBS samples exposed to high temperatures and humidity, biological products decompose rapidly, which can lead to an increase in false-positive (false-positive) or false-negative (false-negative) analysis results. It is also recommended to store samples in plastic bags along with oxygen absorbers. It protects not only from external pollutants, but also from oxygen and moisture in the air. However, it is advisable to use special containers with temperature and humidity control during transportation.

Results. Research shows that improper storage of DBS samples, especially in newborn screening tests, has led to misdiagnosis. This leads to negative consequences, such as involving patients in unjustified treatment, psychological pressure, and inefficient use of resources. For this reason, medical institutions, laboratories, and transportation services must follow strict protocols for storing

and transporting DBS samples. Temperature and humidity control using special equipment significantly improves the accuracy and reliability of the analysis results.

Conclusion. The stability of DBS samples is closely related to how they are stored and transported, which in turn means that proper storage of DBS samples directly affects patients' lives, ensuring the accuracy of diagnostic screening results. That's why strict protocols, technical controls, and staff qualifications are considered among the most important factors in this field. Thus, based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that ensuring the stability of DBS samples is an integral part of high—quality and reliable laboratory analysis

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